

The Critical Body: Toward a Pedagogy of Disruption

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Introduction

In the present essay we attempt to explore the question of the body and its relation to what is called critical thinking. By engaging with the philosophy of Jacques Rancière, we want to suggest a view of critical thinking that takes the body into account. We call this a move toward embodied critical thinking, which includes a disruption of the mind-body dichotomy. This disruption, in turn, is part of what we propose to call a pedagogy of disruption. We specifically focus on disability studies and the dominance of speech and hearing, not only in philosophy, but also in theories of education. We suggest renewed approaches to teaching by giving practical examples which include specific pedagogical situations where a disruptive pedagogy can alter the prevalent hierarchy of mind over body.

Perhaps Rancière's most well-known concept is what he terms the '*partage du sensible*,' often translated as a 'distribution of the sensible.' The keyword in Rancière's concept is *partage*, because of its double meaning, since it signifies both partaking of and inclusion as well as partition, a closing off, and excluding. Interestingly, the ambiguity of *partage* that Rancière emphasizes in his use of the word has also been embraced by Jacques Derrida, and we would like to begin by referring to the last sentence in Jacques Derrida's (2005) reading of Paul Celan's poetry in the published version of his lecture "Shibboleth: For Paul Celan." What is noteworthy, considering the philosophies of Derrida and Rancière, is that Derrida had used the double meaning of *partage* already in 1984 in his lecture on Celan.¹ We see this in the last sentence of "Shibboleth" which

¹ We are, to put it bluntly, hinting at the notion of *ἀρχή*, as used by Rancière, implying someone who leads, or who walks in front, as well as an origin or beginning. For reference, Aristotle identifies six different meanings of *ἀρχή*, which are catalogued and explained in his *Metaphysics* (1012b33-1013a23). Now, in his essay paying homage to Derrida, "Does Democracy Mean Something?" Rancière (2010a) starts out by stating: "I have never been a disciple of Derrida, nor a specialist of his thought. Since I had him as a teacher, very many years ago, there has been no opportunity to discuss philosophical questions with him. The tribute that I can pay him, then, cannot take the form of a commentary on his work" (p. 45). This statement provides, perhaps, an understatement of Rancière's knowledge of Derrida's work. And although it is next to impossible to show intentional influence with absolute certainty, the fact that Derrida uses the word *partage* in the same manner as Rancière later developed it and made it a salient part of his thinking is interesting, given the prominence of the word in Rancière's philosophy. Moreover, the benefits one can get out of reading Rancière with or through Derrida are considerable. One such benefit, we suggest in the present essay, is a comparative analysis of speech (*λόγος*) and voice (*φωνή*)—prominent notions in both Rancière's and Derrida's work. Could we, then, say that Derrida's

runs as follows:

Permettez-moi de laisser tomber ceci, en forme d'envoi ou de *schibboleth*, c'est-à-dire dans l'économie d'une ellipse. Elle n'a cours que dans telle ou telle langue donnée en partage, ici la mienne, en forme de signature aujourd'hui : la circoncision—date. (Derrida, 1985, “Schibboleth: Pour Paul Celan,” p. 113)

Permit me to let fall, by way of envoy or *shibboleth*, that is to say, in the economy of an ellipsis that circulates only in the partaking and partition of a given language, here my own, by way of signature here, today, this: circumcision—dates. (Derrida, 2005, “Shibboleth: For Paul Celan,” p. 64)

There is much to be said about the translation as regards the French version and its English translation, not to speak of the intricate and difficult implications the passage has even in its original French. For example, the French word ‘*envoi*’ does not only mean ‘envoy,’ as the English translation would have it, but also signifies the concluding passage or explanatory remarks of a poem, and the sending of a message, and, to return to the keyword ‘*partage*,’ to the partaking and partition, that is to say to the inclusion and exclusion, of a certain language. These words and their potential translations, we contend, raise the question of possession and by extension of appropriation, which in turn raises the issue of the body and of the possessing and appropriating of one’s own or an other’s body. When we engage in critique we thus engage with the question of the body and the *partage*, or, what amount to the same thing, the aporia that installs itself in the very thinking of body and mind as separate phenomena. It is a question, to be more precise, of including while excluding, which it is imperative to address when considering ableism¹ in education and critical thinking.

Hence, what we would like to develop further in the following is how the body, as the *partage* of the mind, can emerge within a pedagogy of disruption as embodied critical thinking. We will, consequently, broach the question of the body of language and the language of the body. When these languages translate each other, they do so by way of disruption—by breaking apart the presuppositions governing the mind-body dichotomy, and by staging the *partage* at play in any understanding of and any practice of body and language.

Rancière and Aristotle: Dissensus and *Λόγος*

thinking is the *ἀρχή* of at least some parts of Racière’s philosophy? Perhaps more than Rancière wants to admit.

¹ Ableism refers to the oppressive conditions produced by the set of beliefs and actions in society which value abled bodies over disabled bodies. That which is typical for the human species, the corporeal standard, is projected as the perfect, species-typical and therefore essential and fully human (Campbell 2008). In critical disability studies theory, the concept of ableism is employed to focus on perceptions of majority society which reproduce the notion that disability is a diminished state of being (Campbell, 2009). The objective of studies in ableism is to lay bare hierarchializing assumptions and to disrupt them, which provides openings for interrogating normality.

An important concept that Rancière's philosophy circles around is the concept of dissensus. In Rancière's (2011) own contribution to the anthology *Reading Rancière*, "The Thinking of Dissensus: Politics and Aesthetics," he sets out to answer the question "What does it mean to think politics and aesthetics under the concept of dissensus?" In explaining what he means by dissensus, Rancière (2011) refers to his reading of Aristotle:

Aristotle tells us that slaves *understand* language but don't *possess* it. This is what dissensus means. There is politics because speaking is not the same as speaking, because there is not even an agreement on what a sense means. Political dissensus is not a discussion between speaking people who would confront their interests and values. It is a conflict about who speaks and who does not speak, about what has to be heard as the voice of pain and what has to be heard as an argument on justice. (p. 2; emphasis in the original.)

This passage makes clear that for Rancière, dissensus in politics is a concept that designates conflict, and more precisely a conflict about language, which means language as connected to the body, since he states that "slaves *understand* language but don't *possess* it." This is so since slaves do not possess their body—they are possessions, and they, in consequence, are possessed by their possessor's language. They are, to put it bluntly, possessions possessed by a foreign language. To be sure, this is true, also, of certain groups of people in society today. Nevertheless, Rancière's statement that "Aristotle tells us that slaves *understand* language but don't *possess* it" leads us to attend to the passage in Aristotle to which Rancière is referring. The passage reads as follows:

Where then there is such a difference as that between soul and body, or between men and animals (as in the case of those whose business is to use their body, and who can do nothing better), the lower sort are by nature slaves, and it is better for them as for all inferiors that they should be under the rule of a master. For he who can be, and therefore is, another's, and he who participates in reason enough to apprehend, but not to have, is a slave by nature. Whereas the lower animals cannot even apprehend reason [*logou*]; they obey their passions. And indeed the use made of slaves and of tame animals is not very different; for both with their bodies minister to the needs of life. Nature would like to distinguish between the bodies of freemen and slaves, making the one strong for servile labour, the other upright, and although useless for such services, useful for political life in the arts both of war and peace. (Aristotle, 1991, *Politics*, 1254a24-1255a3)

What Aristotle describes here is the result of a separation, with its origin in the sign. As Rancière (1999) states at the outset of *Disagreement: Politics and Philosophy*, the sign is closely connected to politics—that is, the sign as representing speech on the one hand and the voice on the other. Speech, which is the translation of *λόγος*, is in Rancière's reading of Aristotle connected to questions of ethics, to "good and evil," while voice, which is the translation of *φωνή*, is reserved for those who can only feel "pleasure and suffering." This is a difference, Rancière holds, "between two modes of access to sense experience" (p. 2). What is more, this difference and separation is what characterizes "politicity of a superior kind, which is achieved in the family and the city-state" (p. 2). It is, in other words, a question of the supremacy of the *λόγος* over the *φωνή*, *viz.*, of the relation between what Rancière views as the difference between *λόγος* and *φωνή*, namely

the difference of the sign as expression (speech) and the sign as indication (voice). This is what Rancière means when he states that “speaking is not the same as speaking.” However, a pressing question to ask here is one of translation: How should we, to begin with, translate *λόγος* in the passage cited from Aristotle’s *Politics*? Rancière refers to it in the above passage as speech, while most translators of Aristotle translate it as reason. The word is, of course, infamously polysemous, which means that how we choose to translate the word, and so assign to it a specific meaning, brings with it precisely a *partage du sensible*. In other words, the translation installs a way of seeing and understanding, which inevitably not only distributes, but also shuts off possible ways of seeing and understanding. It is, indeed, as Rancière points out, a question of what *λόγος* comes to mean, as in the question “Do you understand?” This question installs *λόγος* as more than a simple answer to the question. For example, as Rancière explains, the question does not only ask for understanding, but also asks for obedience. And apprehending *λόγος* means being obedient and obviously makes the question rhetorical. The question “Do you understand?” thus transforms into an imperative, meaning, in effect, “Do as I say!” Hence, as Rancière insists, “he who participates in reason enough to apprehend, but not to have, is a slave by nature.”

Now, when it comes to politics and the translation of *λόγος*, we must first look to Rancière’s (1999) definition of politics in *Disagreement: Politics and Philosophy*, where he states that the inception of politics involves “a major wrong”: “The wrong by which politics occurs is not some flaw calling for reparation. It is the introduction of an incommensurable at the heart of the distribution of speaking bodies” (p. 19). The incommensurable, we suggest, is also the double character of *λόγος*, and we find this incommensurability in Aristotle. Again, it is a question of translation, and, as we will see, even the impossibility of translation. Thus, in the *Nicomachean Ethics*, speaking on the subject of happiness, Aristotle (1934) introduces the notion of excellence in relation to politics, from which he goes on to broach the question of the rational and irrational parts of the soul. He finds that the rational and irrational share the same doubleness of the *λόγος*:

Thus we see that the irrational (*ἄλογον*) part, as well as the soul as a whole, is double. One division of it, the vegetative, does not share in rational principle at all; the other, the seat of the appetites and of desire in general, does in a sense participate in principle, as being amenable and obedient to it (in the sense in fact in which we speak of “paying heed” [*ἔχειν λόγον* (*echein logon*)] to one’s father and friends, not in the sense of the term “rational” in mathematics). And that principle can in a manner appeal to the irrational part, is indicated by our practice of admonishing delinquents, and by our employment of rebuke and exhortation generally. (1102b25)

This passage (especially the parenthetical note), as the translator of Aristotle underscores, is next to untranslatable.¹ The doubleness and tautological character of *λόγος* (*λόγος* is *λόγος*) thus gives

¹ H. Rackham states in a note to his translation of the passage, “This parenthetical note on the phrase ‘to have logos’ is untranslatable, and confusing even in the Greek. According to the psychology here expounded, the intellect ‘has a plan or principle,’ in the sense of understanding principle, and being able to reason and make a plan: in other words, it is fully rational. The appetitive part of man’s nature ‘has a plan or principle’ in so far as it is capable of following or obeying a principle. It happens that this relationship of following or obeying can itself be expressed by the words ‘to have logos’ in another sense of that phrase, viz. ‘to take account of, pay heed to.’ To be precise the writer should say that the appetitive part *λόγον ἔχει τοῦ λόγου* ‘has

Rancière a foundation for engaging in the necessary assignment of meanings to *λόγος*, which in turn differentiates between those who possess, that is, those who have the ability or disposition (*ἔξις*) to understand, and those who simply can perceive or feel (*αἴσθησις*) and so do not possess understanding. Rancière’s analysis of the ambivalence of *λόγος* in this way points to a disruption of Aristotle’s argument, specifically in *Politics*,¹ about the “natural” hierarchy pertaining to man, woman, slave, and animal, in which man is considered the *ἀρχή*, the one who walks in front, leading, and possessing understanding, while the other categories of being are obeying and following, since they are merely capable of perceiving and feeling. This then, to reiterate, is what Rancière (1999) holds as being “the introduction of an incommensurable at the heart of the distribution of speaking bodies” (p. 19). And “distribution,” here, should be read in the double sense of *partage*, as that which includes while excluding.

This brief outline of what pertains to our argument in Rancière’s thinking is necessarily incomplete, but nevertheless points to the disruptive character of translation and understanding—the incommensurability of the tautology *λόγος* is *λόγος*—which makes up the ground or foundation (*ἀρχή*) of what Rancière calls, precisely, the incommensurable. It also opens up for a continued questioning regarding who speaks and who is allowed to speak, to include the question of the way that speaking is heard or seen or sensed. We want, to put it differently, to question the dominance of both *λόγος* and *φωνή*, and expand the notion of speaking to include all senses and the body as modalities of language and, as such, important aspects of being critical. Being critical, traditionally defined as having the knowledge and understanding necessary for a thinking defined as critical, would instead come to mean that the “critical” is displaced from the purely rational discourse of *λόγος*, when defined as reason, to include sensibility, the senses of seeing and touching (*αἴσθησις*), which means a disruption of the *λόγος*, of the way critical thinking, as one of the major goals of education is traditionally conceived.

Rancière and Heidegger: Ontology, Politics, and Aesthetics

In the aforementioned chapter, “The Thinking of Dissensus: Politics and Aesthetics” (2011), Rancière presents us with what could be called an explanatory summary of his philosophy. In his explanation he touches on how he views the difference between his thinking and ontology:

The global logic of my work aims at showing that pure politics and pure aesthetics are doomed to be overturned together in the radicalization of the infinite wrong or infinite evil. I try to think disagreement as the wrong that cannot be settled but can be processed all the same. This means that I try to keep the conceptualization of exception, wrong

logos (takes account) of the logos.’ The phrase has yet a third sense in mathematics, where ‘to have logos’ (ratio) means ‘to be rational’ in the sense of commensurable” (Aristotle, 1934, *Nicomachean Ethics*, note 6).

¹ See *Politics*, 1254b5-26. It should be emphasized that Rancière is dealing here with the complex notion of *ἔξις* in *Politics*. He is not, it seems, specifically addressing the different meanings of *ἔξις* in Aristotle’s work generally, but is focusing rather on *ἔξις* and *αἴσθησις* as describing the double nature of *λόγος* and its formative implications for the concepts of politics, democracy, and emancipation, which make up a seminal part of his thinking. For a discussion of *ἔξις* in Aristotle’s philosophy more generally, see, e.g., Rodrigo (2011).

or excess apart from any kind of ontology. The current trend has it that you cannot think politics unless you trace back its principles to an ontological principle: Heideggerian difference, Spinozist infinity of Being in Negri's conception, polarity of being and event in Badiou's thought, re-articulation of the relationship between potency and act in Agamben's theory, etc. My assumption is that such a requirement leads to the dissolution of politics on behalf of some historico-ontological destiny process. (pp. 11-12)

Given these statements, it can be clarifying to look more closely at Heidegger's analysis of politics and aesthetics, that is, at what Rancière refers to as the "historico-ontological destiny process" in Heidegger's thinking which, according to Rancière, dissolves politics. We have chosen to refer to Heidegger's *Hölderlin's Hymn "The Ister"* to compare his thinking with Rancière's, since this work addresses the concepts under discussion, namely politics, aesthetics, and *λόγος*. In his analysis of the Greek conception of *πόλις*, Heidegger (1996) states the following:

Toward the beginning of his *Politics*, Aristotle designates the human being as *ζῷον πολιτικόν*. Translated in a superficial way, this oft-quoted word means: "the human being is a political being." In ascertaining this, however, people are content to let their knowledge of Aristotle's *Politics* rest. No one asks why the human being is and is able to be a "political being." One pays no attention to the fact that Aristotle also provides the answer to this question at the beginning of his *Politics*. The human being is a *ζῷον πολιτικόν* because the human being, and only the human being, is a *ζῷον λόγος ἔχων*—a living being that has the word, which means: *that* being that can address beings as such with respect to their being. (p. 83)

For our purposes, it is noteworthy that *λόγος* in *ζῷον λόγος ἔχων* is rendered as "the word" by Heidegger, which is of course important, given his emphasis on speech and language.¹ Hence, Heidegger holds that the human being is able to be a political being in so far as it is a living being (*Lebewesen*) that has the word, which means its ability to ask about the being of beings. In other words, the human being is, first and foremost, a living being of language, and of the word, which does not necessarily mean that it is a rational being. Instead of distributing living beings between those who are rational and those who are not, as Aristotle does, Heidegger separates the beings who have language from those who do not possess language. And language here, for Heidegger, as well as for Rancière, means sounding speech.

Now, what Rancière opposes in Heidegger is what he calls, in the passage above, "the dissolution of politics on behalf of some historico-ontological destiny process," in other words, the way Heidegger conceives of how being manifests itself for Dasein, as it appears or is "given" in its epochal destining for appropriation (*Ereignis*). Heidegger's analysis of the Greek *πόλις* in *Hölderlin's Hymn "The Ister"* is a case in point of exactly that "historico-ontological destiny process" which Rancière wants to avoid in his thinking of the wrong(s) that constitute(s) politics, that is, the *ἀρχή* of politics. The *πόλις*, Heidegger asserts, "is neither merely state, nor merely city, rather in the first instance it is properly 'the stead' [*die Statt*]: the site [*die Stätte*] of the abode of

¹ Two texts in which Heidegger addresses the topic of *λόγος* in detail are *Plato's The Sophist* (1997) and *Introduction to Phenomenological Research* (2005). For a discussion on Heidegger's reading of *λόγος* in Aristotle, see e.g. S. Elden (2005).

human history that belongs to humans in the midst of beings. This, however, precisely does not mean that the political has priority” (p. 82). Instead, the *πόλις* is that site which makes politics possible in the first place. It is where human beings are determined as beings, or what Heidegger calls the fitting-destining destiny which determines history: “For whatever is fitting [*das Schickliche*] determines destiny [*das Geschick*], and such destiny determines history [*die Geschichte*]” (p. 82). On the basis of this, Heidegger can sum up the essence of the *πόλις*:

The pre-political essence of the *πόλις*, that essence that first makes possible everything political in the originary and in the derivative sense, lies in its being the open site of that fitting destining [*Schickung*] from out of which all human relations toward beings—and that always means in the first instance the relations of beings as such to humans—are determined. The essence of the *πόλις* therefore always comes to light in accordance with the way in which beings as such in general enter the realm of the unconcealed. (*Hölderlin’s Hymn “The Ister,”* 1996, p. 82)

This, then, is an instance of the “historico-ontological destinary process” which Rancière claims dissolves politics. Instead of a collective destinary movement of the history of the being of beings, Rancière emphasizes the singularity of wrongs which constitute politics, that is, politics is reconstituted with each ‘new’ and unique wrong that is voiced out of the distribution of the sensible that suppresses those without *λόγος* as reason. The notion of a destinary process is what Rancière calls “messianism,” and besides Heidegger and the names mentioned in the passage quoted above (Badiou, Negri, and Agamben), Rancière also includes Derrida as belonging to this movement. What messianism implies is an advent, a waiting for something or someone to come; in Heidegger’s case it is the being of beings, in Derrida’s case it is, Rancière claims, the notion of the Other.

Now, what Rancière (2010b) views as the essence of politics is, as noted, dissensus, by which he means “the demonstration (*manifestation*) of a gap in the sensible itself,” as he states in the eighth of his “Ten Theses on Politics” (p. 38). Furthermore, this gap in the sensible has to do with language and the ability to reason and understand. Rancière refers to Book I of Aristotle’s *Politics*, in which Aristotle defines the human being as a political being. As Rancière interprets Aristotle, “the sign of the political nature of humans is constituted by their possession of the *logos*, which is alone able to demonstrate a community in the *aesthesis* of the just and the unjust, in contrast to the *phôné*, appropriate only for expressing feelings of pleasure and displeasure” (p. 37). This, in turn, leads Rancière to deduce the following from Aristotle’s *Politics*: “If there is someone you do not wish to recognize as a political being, you begin by not seeing him as the bearer of signs of politicinity, by not understanding what he says, by not hearing what issues from his mouth as discourse” (p. 38). Thus, to break out of the gap of dissensus, or the distribution of the sensible, those who are suppressed must make themselves seen and heard. In other words, it is a question of *αἰσθητικῆς*, of perception and of being perceived. But in order to do this one has to have *λόγος*, that is, *λόγος ἔχων*, and the dominant and preferred *λόγος* is sounding speech. This is where Heidegger and Rancière intersect, despite their differences when it comes to thinking the *πόλις*, politics, aesthetics, and *λόγος*; that is, and again, they both favor a reading of *λόγος* as speech.¹

¹ As Heidegger (1997) states in *Plato’s Sophist*: “Thus *ἀληθευειν* shows itself most immediately in *λέγειν*. *λέγειν* (“to speak”) is what most basically constitutes human Dasein. In speaking, Dasein expresses itself—by speaking about something, about the world. This *λέγειν* was for the Greeks

It is, in consequence, necessary to examine this *ableism* closer, in order to disrupt it and so make way for a disruptive pedagogy, and we find the beginning of such a critique in Derrida's reading of Husserl in *Speech and Phenomena*, namely a deconstruction of the self-presence of the voice, that is, what we have up until now called sounding speech.

Rancière and Derrida: The Deconstruction of $\Phi\omega\nu\eta$

The deconstruction of $\phi\omega\nu\eta$ is necessary in order to conceive of and develop a critical thinking which encompasses the body and the sensible, that is to say, a critical thinking which, precisely, incorporates the sensuous and somatic with $\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma$ as rationality and self-present living speech. The conception of such critical thinking would, we suggest, entail the development of a disruptive pedagogy, with the power to subvert the ableism of philosophy, conservative pedagogy, and traditional notions of academic critical thinking.

Thus, from the deconstruction of $\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma$ as speech, and so also of the voice ($\phi\omega\nu\eta$), a deconstruction perhaps most carefully executed in the chapter "The Voice That Keeps Silent" of Derrida's reading of Husserl in *Speech and Phenomena*, it becomes clear that what Derrida terms the "supplement of origin," the *différance* before the difference of inside and outside, and of the self-presence of the voice, encompasses a translation that contains¹ a disruption of the $\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma$ as speech-voice and/as self-presence. Furthermore, it means that any distribution of the sensible cannot rely on the speech-voice of those who do not possess $\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma$ as reason, speech as expression, authority, etc., but must take into account ($\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma$) the disruption of logocentrism as the dominance and supremacy of the voice and of living self-present speech. In a crucial passage in chapter six of *Speech and Phenomena*, Derrida (1973) states the following:

This self-presence of the animating act in the transparent spirituality of what it animates, this inwardness of life with itself, which has always made us say that speech [*parole*] is alive, supposes, then, that the speaking subject hears himself [*s'entende*] in the present. Such is the essence or norm of speech. It is implied in the very structure of speech that the speaker *hears himself*: both that he perceives the sensible form of the phonemes and that he understands his own expressive intention. If accidents occur which seem to contradict this teleological necessity, either they will be overcome by some supplementary operation or there will be no speech. Deaf and dumb go hand in hand. He who is deaf can engage in colloquy only by shaping his acts in the form of words, whose telos requires that they be heard by him who utters them. (p. 78; emphasis in the original)

so preponderant and such an everyday affair that they acquired their definition of man in relation to, and on the basis of, this phenomenon and thereby determined it as $\zeta\tilde{\omega}\nu\lambda\acute{o}\gamma\omicron\varsigma\ \acute{\epsilon}\chi\omicron\nu'$ (p. 12).

¹ 'Contain' here should be read as meaning both control, restrain, suppress, etc., and include, encompass, etc., since translation, as it is conceived of here, is always idiosyncratic, that is, what Rancière would perhaps call poetical.

As Derrida argues, the perceived ground of speech is presence and the self-presence of the speaker and his/her ability to *hear*. In comparison, when Rancière (2011) states that “[w]hat is important to me is that this ‘reduction’ of scientific discourse to the poetical moment means its reduction to the equality of speaking beings” (p. 14), which is what Heidegger, through Aristotle, calls ζῶον λόγος ἔχων, he accounts for only those in possession of voice, of the φωνή, and thus those who are able to hear, which, importantly, is what makes equality possible. Even if his displacement of scientific discourse in favor of the poetical moment makes possible a rethinking of critical thinking in terms of a disruption of the λόγος as rationality, his insistence on the sign as phoneme, speech-voice, as being part of those without part, leaves him unable to account for and dismantle the logocentrism of the φωνή, which amounts to a forgetting of the dominance of speech and sensory perception (αἴσθησις). Rancière thus relies, as Derrida expresses it, on a “teleological necessity,” namely the teleological necessity of the voice and speech, which is equal to the messianism with which Rancière labels the thinking of Heidegger and Derrida, among others. One could even claim that Rancière’s insistence on the subversive αἴσθησις of speech follows the same movement as Heidegger’s ontological destinary process.

If we are to question and, hopefully, develop the concept of critical thinking, we should nevertheless pay heed to Rancière’s critique of the ἀρχή and the dominance of λόγος as rationality. However, we must not remain content with simply following Rancière, but instead, as we want to suggest, problematize his insistence on speech-voice as metaphors for the disruption of rationality and thinking as the sole means by which critical thinking, and so the struggle for equality, can be conceived. In other words, we have to take his notion of incommensurability seriously. As we suggest, this would mean critical thinking as a pedagogy of disruption, as we envisage it: an embodied criticality which honors each dis-ability as a power of disruption and a possibility for thinking otherwise.

Translation as Disruptive Praxis: Disrupting Ableist Language

Having returned to the texts of Aristotle through Rancière via Derrida (or vice versa), and implicating/involving Heidegger, we are now able to discern a different path by way of the body. Our previous work together in Disability Studies and Deaf Studies conversations puts in reach a way to disrupt through the concepts of ableism and audism.¹ Following the lead of disability scholars in challenging norms and ideas of normality (Davis, 1995), and drawing on the theoretical potential of the ubiquitous phenomenon of disability as a “new normal” (Ginsburg and Rapp, 2001), we are able to contribute to developing a pedagogy of disruption. This ‘disrupting through disability’ is possible because of how the landscape of understanding shifts in the wake of the creation of new categories through medical technology, i.e., increased longevity through health care, the prematurely born, the newly diagnosed, and the new ways to be deaf, with cochlear implants (Ginsburg and Rapp, 2001, Adams Lyngbäck, 2016). Both concepts, disruption and disability, are disorienting in the ways they puncture similitude, this being of thought in the one case and of corporeality in the other. Sara Ahmed calls this a politics of disorientation (Ahmed, 2006, p. 21), where we analyze with both temporality (past texts, re-readings, translation) and spatiality (the body). This placing in time and space disrupts assumptions about the body in

¹ Audism is a type of ableism which perpetuates negative attitudes towards those who do not hear, which result in the stigmatization of deafness and of the use of sign languages.

philosophy, as presented in our argument above. Through an example in the classroom, the body as a site for disruption expands what it means to think critically. In this way we join others who through method “place disability in conversation with other concepts and worlds” (Friedner and Weingarten, 2019, p. 485). The choices a teacher makes are described as pedagogical disruptions which direct learners towards particular ways of understanding and away from other ones.

We now turn to a discussion of the body and the senses through which the communication of thought can be shared. The example we use involves the way hearing-deaf relationships have been studied and how historically there is evidence that the difficulty of translation from one modality is an existential matter in intimate relationships: the hearing parent and the deaf child in each unique meeting between people reach across their signed or spoken ways of being in the world (Adams Lyngbäck, 2016). The challenge faced by parents who are not deaf is that they often experience regret at not being like their child, which due to phonocentrism and audism is largely missing in the stories of their grieving. This aspect becomes clearer in studies centering on the body and affect in experience as parents move beyond wishing the child were hearing to wishing they as caretakers could communicate more easily and share in their child’s way of existing. What evolves in deaf-hearing relationships is that the knowledge of the difference of the other’s way of existing is known to each, and it is this spatial and ontological territory of the meeting of the two that provides our entry point into a pedagogical relation. This will shed light on how the incommensurable is a site for disruption of dominant forms of thought.

Logocentrism, in Derrida’s sense, is comparable to the concepts of ableism, audism, and linguisticism—systems of dominance privileging forms of expression of thought (Encyclopedia of Disability, 2006; Wolbring, 2012; Humphries, 1975; Bauman, 2004, 2008; Eckert and Rowley, 2013; Skutnabb-Kangas, 2012). As with translation, if one system is forced through another, it will be distorted, mangled out of shape, and the meaning intended to be conveyed will become difficult to reach, like dimming the lights and turning up the sound in order to look at a painting or see a facial expression. This is a likeness to how critical thinking, when involving knowledge of another’s knowledge and knowledge of another’s experience, will always require an interrogating of one’s own way of being in the world. Susan Wendell points to this acknowledgment of relationality and its role in vulnerability (2008, p. 832). To study the role of the body in critical thinking, notions of privileging are examined in the mediums, modalities, abilities, sensory systems or language systems, and analyzed as a disruption of normative thought systems (Applebaum, 2017; DiAngelo, 2011; Gilson, 2011).

Examples of the hearing discovering the world of the deaf are well documented (Sachs, 1990; Lane, 1989, 1992; Lane, Hoffmeister and Bahan, 1996; Ladd, 2010). It perhaps is a clearer path to take to show how the philosophers discussed in this essay do not utilize the potential of visual language systems in their own thinking. This is a similar re-analysis to how feminist philosophers are able to lay bare the shortcomings of privileging one type of sex/gender over others, and how the societal roles in the days of those philosophers hindered their thinking in ways that are known to those outside of particular historical points who have other types of bodies (Davis, 1995; Zeiler and Käll, 2014; Ahmed, 2013). In the case of dis-ability, by the same token, this means each body, each dis-ability, provides alternative and complementary ways of sensing and being in the world, which can further what can be known about how humans think and communicate (Davis, 1995; Barnes, 2016).

For our purposes, in pedagogical relations, the notion of disruption as a way to break out of one's own way of thinking is not only a priority in educational practices, but also holds the potential to serve as a defining characteristic of learning for the betterment of humanity (Baldwin, 1971; hooks, 2003, 2010, 2014). A shift or change in perspective of thought through the body must occur, a primacy of embodiment in experience which we have learned from de Beauvoir (1952) and Merleau-Ponty (2002), as a defining element of criticality. The problem is paradoxical as well; to know more you have to acknowledge ignorance; to be more certain about the nature of the world you have to aim to rest in uncertainty and aporia about what you already know or can expect (hooks, 2014).

In Disability Studies and Deaf Studies, the lives of people who are disabled, are hard-of-hearing, deaf or culturally Deaf, are the points of departure for these disciplines. We are careful to point out that in this essay, there is a moral sensitivity to utilizing ways of being in differentness to support our point, that experiences can unsettle oppressive 'isms' in philosophy and in higher education through redefining critical thinking as disruption. At the same time, it is a crucial step towards not reproducing the limitations we have identified in how language, body, and thought have historically been contemplated. A necessary contribution then is to challenge even these philosophically foundational assumptions. One way to do this is to examine the intellectualized view, position, way of thought, or way of seeing an issue in higher education, in classrooms, and in conservative pedagogy. Excluding the Other in research, the primary reason why the aforementioned disciplines emerged, is one manifestation of oppression which is repeated when loyalty to systems of knowledge production (universities) comes before loyalty to admitting to not knowing. Two components, the unveiling of logocentric-abled-audist-linguicist privilege and the instigating of a disruptive force of pedagogical movement based on the lived body and differentness, provide learners with sensory experiences which can in no other way be reached than through the stories of others, be it through literature, personal encounters, or intimate relationships. (We have but one body in which to think but require the bodies of others to think critically.) In Rancièrian terms, an aesthetics of disability involves sharing in a sense experience (as politics) through a distribution of the senses, for others to see/hear/feel/know about what it means to be disabled, have impairment; or to utilize a visual language, as it is in that moment that subjectivities arise and the dialogue with a political subject begins. To make this way of intervening (staging disruption, translation, *partage*) into a pedagogical action which broadens knowledge through approaching uncertainty (aporia, shibboleth, incommensurability, dissensus), responsibility for allowing the process to occur is not a question of 'freeing the ignorant from their ignorance' but of acknowledging the political role held through educational privilege and letting the body speak, through its tangible pain and vulnerability.

Disability literacy and allyship (Adams Lyngbäck, 2016) through embodied critical thinking transform the philosophical underpinnings of phenomenology and metaphysical dualism into disruptive pedagogy as praxis. It embarks from ambiguity about embracing difference and continues through exposing ableism in language and thought. This movement provides insight into alternative understandings about what knowledge is, and reveals the unfinished, cyclical, unsettled nature of criticality. A way to shift what one knows lies in the approach to the problem, dilemma, or study of a phenomenon. As numerous scholars of difference have taught us, to first acknowledge vulnerability, relationality, and the complicity of injustices which lie therein is how

learning occurs (LaChance Adams, 2014; Ahmed, 2006; DiAngelo, 2011; hooks 2000; Gilson, 2011; Wendell, 2008). Here the approach necessarily includes the letting go of “givens” through examining assumptions, and in so doing gives rise to new subjectivities, which brings us back to Rancière’s distribution of the sensible.

Disruption in Pedagogical Engagement in the Classroom

The student, a hearing, non-signing teacher in a deaf school, often spoke about the importance of taking on the task of helping the deaf to learn (Lane, 1992). The shortage of qualified and certified teachers who could also sign was often acknowledged and discussed as a structural discrimination in the group. This student taught with the support of an interpreter. She expressed a desire to want to learn to sign, but thought that the main objective was to instruct. Having a pragmatic attitude, she countered the repeated message of the rights of the Deaf to be taught in sign language with arguments about how a sincere teacher was more important than knowing sign language. When the subject came up in her workplace, which was dominated by hearing teachers, she felt supported in this position. In the university classes in the special education needs program for the deaf and hearing impaired, where there is a large number of proficient signers, the collective view was that bicultural and sign-bilingual environment was more important for learners, and this serves as the origin of the conflict.

This situation led the student to defend her view, a solidifying of her previous knowledge, rather than toward what the objective of higher education entails: a shift in thinking through critical reflection. She stated that she was being shut out, discouraged, discriminated against as a hearing person in the deaf education arena, particularly in how deaf advocates and organizations insisted on proficient signing in the education of the deaf. “I’m so tired of hearing about how I’m not good enough!” is the way she expressed it with tears in her eyes—an expression of what Appelbaum (2017) names ethical and epistemological closure, and DiAngelo describes as fragility in respect to racism (2011). An incomplete likeness, but one sufficient for this example, is the term *hearing fragility*, which refers to how the position of being victimized is occupied and utilized to ward off having to acknowledge collective harm to deaf individuals and deaf culture.

This incident occurred in response to a lecture on a recent ten-year struggle to reinstate a program which allows deaf teachers to have their own seminar conducted in a national sign language embedded in the structure of the university’s compulsory schoolteacher education program. Previously the requirement for permanent positions in the schools for the deaf had been an advanced degree in special education needs for the deaf and hearing impaired. This first required deaf teachers to gain a teaching degree, acquire teaching experience for a minimum of three years, and then apply for the advanced program, which required an additional one and a half years of fulltime studies in order to be able to teach in the official language of instruction in the schools for the deaf. As it was presented, this policy had changed due to the lack of teachers and the exodus of those with advanced degrees from the deaf schools to higher paying positions, and not necessarily to the language rights of the deaf. The student’s tearful reaction in the following discussion was in response to the lecturer’s conclusion that deaf students should be taught by deaf teachers or other native or native-level proficient signers.

There is a paradox about the body in the classroom; on the one hand there is hearing fragility through becoming a victim, which is an oppressive form of ignorance, and on the other hand there

is epistemic vulnerability as a necessity for learning (Gilson, 2011). The show of emotion through the body is the moment where the teacher can pinpoint a starting towards the understanding of others' experiences, but it can also derail the project of learning from others' life conditions. In the above example, the moment was occupied by the hearing student's not being able to remain in uncertainty about the dilemma of the language gap. There were not only tears, but also aggression in the form of accusations that the deaf were being closed-minded. It is here that the crucial step can occur in order to disrupt. The disruptive moment and pedagogical potential can only be attained if the teacher can also utilize the dissensus without it resulting in a closing off of what can be learned about another's vulnerability, in this case that of the deaf students. How deaf people exist involves a language of the body, which was the instigator of the disruptive pedagogical moment. What is pedagogically necessary is to redirect this crying state, an expression of hearing fragility, back to where there is no victim, or dichotomy of oppressed-oppressor, but to a point where the conversation returns to audism, collective complicity, and shared responsibility for change.

The affect, the crying, the tone of voice, the standing up and moving to reach for the microphone, the loudly moving furniture with her body created a nearly aggressive atmosphere. This arrangement imprinted the incident in memory for some who witnessed it, giving it a possible potential for disruption even in the future for others not present. The outburst was then framed by the instructor as an 'understandable reaction,' but in this frustration there is a chance to see elements of the dilemma: inequality in education, lack of proficient teachers who can sign, the necessity for but inadequacy of hearing-deaf teacher teams, the discriminatory education policies involved in teacher qualifications, the role of bi-directional language comprehension and psychosocial identity in learning and conceptual development, etc. In this way, the instructor was able to divert away from the 'crying hearing girl' as victim, which would have derailed the discussion (hooks, 2010). Knowledge of how to use a disruptive moment as pedagogy requires awareness of the way societal norms lead to going to great lengths to not have to translate social issues into violence in addressing emotion in the classroom. Critically thinking about what is allowed to be said and done in a classroom in regard to making people uncomfortable or even allowing the uncomfortable to disrupt leads to showing how the student is responsible, as we all are, for the injustices which were embodied by the deaf professor. Classmates pointed out that a teacher who does not sign is better than no teacher, but that does not mean deaf students' rights are not being violated and that we (hearing and deaf alike) do not need to do more to work for a solution.

The ones who have the most 'translation work' to do in this scenario, because of the production of and adherence to audist norms, are the hearing, a basic tenet of what privilege in a social and political sense imbues. There is a choice between holding fast to the idea of 'this is how things are' and engaging in the emotional labor of learning what is vital to the task of guaranteeing deaf people's rights to learn. Avoidance of uncomfortable moments in classrooms make much disruption impossible. The above, as an example of a pedagogy of disruption involving the body and its untranslatable nature, and exhibiting the theorizing about language and embodiment, makes explicit how university teaching underutilizes the pervasiveness of human vulnerability as a vehicle of learning. Erinn Gilson (2011) examines the 'epistemology of ignorance' which sheds light on our discussion of disruptive pedagogical moments:

[E]pistemic vulnerability is what makes learning, and thus a reduction of ignorance,

possible. Undoing ignorance involves cultivating the attitude of one who is epistemically vulnerable rather than that of the masterful, invulnerable knower who has nothing to learn from other. (Gilson, 2011, p. 324)

In “Crying Time,” a chapter in bell hooks’ *Teaching Critical Thinking*, hooks points out how displays of emotion in classroom settings anchored in real-life events are viewed by educators (2010). In hooks’ texts we detect a paradoxical relationship between potential disruptions of homogenous and hierarchical ways of doing critical thinking and potential distractions from the violence of dominator culture. hooks writes,

Weeping, crying, wailing, all displays of emotional intensity are feared in the classroom because they upset the hierarchy that would have us assume that the mind should always have dominion over the body and spirit. We are called to learn beyond the boundary of language, of words, where we share common understanding. We are called to learn from our sense, from our feeling states, and find their ways of knowing. If we allow for the possibility of tears, then an insurrection of subjugated knowledge may occur. (hooks, 2010, p. 83)

Lived experience as a development of theory owes its credibility to embodiment as epistemology (Ahmed, 2018; Ahmed, 2017) and to how the language of the body, as untranslatable, will continually require that a choice be made by an educator on whether to allow or silence a moment. Being able to allow the possibility of embodied emotion precedes the choosing between disruption and distraction. However, more than simply being able to allow for possibility, it involves actively planning for the recognition of the body as language as a way to deepen and develop critical thinking. We best deal and interact with the crying student, then, in and through the act of recognizing the incommensurability, the aporetic, as the defining characteristic of the point in time and space in which disruption emanates or dissipates, is soothed or felt as discomfort. A pedagogy of disruption involves the body and the critical.

Conclusion

The urgent need for a disruptive pedagogy that the above example gives us to contemplate cannot be overestimated. What we have argued for in this essay is the necessity of breaking with the prevailing suppression of the body in conservative and traditional education, a suppression which extends to the importance granted to critical thinking in higher education. We have, moreover, suggested that a disruptive pedagogy can provide a way out of the hegemony of Cartesian rationality. Thus, by taking our cue from Jacques Rancière’s philosophy, while at the same time remaining critical of it, we have proposed a re-evaluation of the voice in philosophical and educational discourse, and a decentering of the dominance of normalcy in education. To think critically, we have argued, we have to have the courage and patience to remain in disrupting pedagogical moments, emotional, bodily straining, and aporetic moments, in order to subvert the simplistic reliance on positivist educational traditions. In sum, we have tried to situate the pedagogy of disruption “in the economy of an ellipsis that circulates only in the partaking and partition of a given language,” to borrow the words with which Jacques Derrida concludes his “Shibboleth.”

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